

Multi-Objective Optimization of Evacuation Route for Passengers in Metro Stations Considering Node Efficiency

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To Cite this Article

Dr. P. Naga Malleswara Rao, G. Jaya Madhavi, B. Raja Shekar, B. Sravani & K.Santhi Priya (2025). Multi-Objective Optimization of Evacuation Route for Passengers in Metro Stations Considering Node Efficiency. International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology, 11(04), 24-31. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15108957>

Article Info

Received: 02 March 2025; Accepted: 28 March 2025.; Published: 30 March 2025.

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KEYWORDS

*Social force model.
Metro station.
Route Optimization.
Passenger Evacuation.
Node efficiency.*

ABSTRACT

Reasonable planning of passenger evacuation routes can directly improve the evacuation efficiency in metro stations. Considering the effect of traffic capacity at nodes such as the gate, stair/escalator, a multi-objective optimization model aimed at minimizing the maximum evacuation time of heterogeneous passengers in different segmentation areas is established, which achieves local optimization on the basis of the global optimization of the evacuation route. Node traffic capacity is assessed by a new prediction model of node travel time based on the combination of BP neural network and atomic orbital search algorithm, which is helpful to ameliorate the route optimization strategy. Mass motion with embedded the social force model and the minimum cost model is applied to simulate passenger movement, and its effectiveness is verified by T-independent sample test and nonparametric independent sample test. The simulation results indicate that the performance of the established prediction model of node travel time is good, and the mean square error can be as low as 0.2555. Meanwhile, the proposed route strategy can improve the overall evacuation efficiency by 21.5%, and passengers' choice of evacuation routes is more reasonable. The sensitivity analysis of factors affecting evacuation through random forest algorithm shows that the number of passengers with person attribute E has the greatest impact on evacuation time, which should be the focus of attention in the evacuation process. The proposed method could help passengers avoid the bottlenecks in advance and realize the safe and efficient evacuation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The process of global urbanization promotes the rapid development of public transport. Metro, as a public transportation tool, greatly facilitates people's daily travel with the advantages of punctuality, large traffic volume, energy conservation, and gradually occupies an important position of public transport in large cities [1]. Most metro stations are built underground, the space is relatively closed, and the average daily passenger flow is generally large. Once an accident occurs, it is more likely to cause serious disasters [2]. In January 2015, a carriage of train in the L'Enfant Plaza Station of Washington, D.C., America, suddenly caught fire and emitted thick smoke, which resulted in the death of one female and the injury of many people during the evacuation [3]. In July 2020, the torrential rain in Zhengzhou, China, caused the flooding of the train of metro line 5, resulting in 14 deaths [4]. Passengers in the metro station may be cleared in case of equipment and facilities failure, potential safety hazards and large-scale power failure. The panic of passengers could have a serious negative impact on evacuation, and may even lead to secondary accidents such as stampede and crush [5, 6]. The significance of a reasonable and efficient evacuation strategy at this time is prominent, which can alleviate the tension and anxiety of passengers and ensure a certain evacuation order. Common evacuation strategies mainly include guiding passengers to evacuate through fixed signage and dynamic guides [7]. The fixed signage can emit light to lead passengers to the exit, but the position of the signage is often unchanged and cannot be adjusted according to the distribution of passengers and the availability of routes. During the peak period in the metro station, when a large number of passengers rush to the exit for evacuation, it is often difficult for the guides to reach the designated location to induce the evacuation. Thanks to the rapid development of computer technology and the widespread application of smart phones, optimized A.

(i) An evacuation route optimization model considering passenger heterogeneity is provided. Taking minimizing the maximum evacuation time of heterogeneous passengers in different segmentation areas as the goal, it can achieve local optimization on the

route information can be sent to passengers in real time through mobile applications, which is convenient, fast and covers a wide range. At this time, it is necessary to study the optimization of evacuation routes in metro stations to formulate evacuation strategies for timely sending to passengers through mobile applications in case of emergency. The route planning of passengers from their own locations to the exits is the main difficulty of formulating evacuation strategies. In the process of route planning, the metro station evacuation network is generally abstracted as a directed graph, in which the gate, stair/escalator and exit are the nodes, and the connection between the passable nodes is the edge [8].

A complete evacuation route can be formed by selecting appropriate nodes and edges between the origin and the destination. In the process of node and edge selection, the length of evacuation route and the degree of route congestion are the two most direct factors that affect the evacuation efficiency [9]. The calculation of evacuation time usually involves the travel time on the edge and the time of passing through the node [10]. The travel time on the edge is closely related to the edge length and congestion, which is often concerned. However, the impact of the traffic efficiency at the node on the overall evacuation is always ignored. It may affect the congestion of the edge, and even may become the key to the choke that affects the overall traffic efficiency. Generally, the traffic efficiency at the node is related to the number of people, flow rate and node width. Among them, the determination of flow rate of node often depends on experience [10], which is easy to lead to large estimation errors, and ignores the impact of passenger heterogeneity. For example, passengers carrying suitcases tend to be relatively inefficient. Therefore, this paper proposes a new method to predict the node traffic efficiency which is based on the combination of BP neural network model and the atomic orbital algorithm.

The main contributions of this paper are as follows. basis of global optimization and effectively improve the evacuation efficiency.

(ii) A new method for predicting the traffic efficiency of key nodes such as gates and stairs is provided. The BP neural network model is improved by the atomic orbital

algorithm to increase the accuracy of the prediction results of node travel time.

The structure of this paper is as follows. Section 2 reviews and analyzes the existing results in the research direction of this paper. Section 3 introduces the pedestrian dynamics model, and puts forward an evacuation route optimization model and a prediction model of node travel time. Section 4 verifies the effectiveness of the passenger dynamics model by comparing the field survey data with the simulation data. The comparison of relevant prediction algorithms of node travel time, the comparison of different evacuation route optimization models and the sensitivity analysis of various factors on the evacuation time are carried out in Section 5. Section 6 summarizes the main results of this paper and puts forward prospects

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

The behavioral characteristics at the strategic level, tactical level and executive level are involved [11] in the process of passenger evacuation in the metro station. Generally, the strategic level information, such as the purpose of evacuation, is known. The tactical level information such as the specific evacuation route and the executive level information such as the specific passenger movement behavior can be simulated through the appropriate modeling. Some special pedestrian motion simulation software [12, 13] have emerged in succession with the rapid development of pedestrian dynamics theory and computer technology. They can be used to simulate passenger evacuation in metro stations, avoiding the dangers of human experiments and the emergence of some ethical issues that may be involved. The relevant literature review of this paper is mainly divided into the following four dynamics model to simulate pedestrian movement, and concluded that the crowd fluid may show abnormal aerodynamic behavior. Hughes et al. [17] established the motion equation to describe the two-dimensional flow of pedestrians. Colombo et al. [18] proposed a fluid dynamics model to describe the typical characteristics of panic crowd. Jiang et al. [19] established a high-order macroscopic model of crowd from the perspective of fluid dynamics to describe the instability of crowd movement. Yuhaski et al. [20] used the M/G/C/C queuing theory model to analyze the traffic flow in the

aspects. (1) Introduction of the existing typical pedestrian motion model. To a certain extent, the accuracy of the simulation results of evacuation is determined by the pedestrian motion model. Choosing an appropriate pedestrian motion model is convenient for the selection of simulation software and the simulation of the real evacuation scene. (2) Analysis of the impact of pedestrian behavior and sites on evacuation efficiency. Some self-organization behaviors of pedestrians such as herding behavior, arching and different scenarios may affect the evacuation efficiency in case of emergency. The evacuation behavior of passengers in metro stations built in underground space is often different from that in other scenarios. (3) Introduction and comparison of existing evacuation strategies. Evaluation strategy directly determines the evacuation efficiency. Clarifying the shortcomings of existing evacuation strategies can help to improve the multi objective route optimization model constructed in this paper. (4) Introduction of existing simulation software. Embedding the evacuation strategy into the simulation software can test the evacuation effect more quickly, and the visualization effect is strong

2.1. Pedestrian motion model

The description of pedestrian movement behavior can be carried out from the macroscopic and microscopic perspectives, respectively. According to the different ways of space-time description, pedestrian motion models can be divided into continuous type and discrete type. Macroscopic models mainly include fluid/gas dynamics model and queuing theory model [14]. The fluid/gas dynamics model regards the movement of people as fluid/gas. Helbing et al. [15] believed that crowd movement was similar to fluid flow at medium and high densities. Henderson [16] proposed a fluid building. Cruz et al. [21] used the M/G/C/C queuing theory model to analyze the allocation of services and capacity in queuing networks. The macroscopic model focuses on the description of the motion rule of the whole crowd, and the model calculation is relatively small, but it often ignores the interaction between pedestrians and individual attributes. Typical microscopic pedestrian motion models include cellular automata model [22], lattice gas model [23] and social force model [24]. Cellular automata model is one of the most commonly used methods in discrete models,

which was proposed by Neumann et al. [25]. It defines the scene as a discrete cell space with finite states, and pedestrians evolve in discrete time according to certain rules. Liu et al. [26] proposed a cellular automata model based on fuzzy logic method, which explained that large public places should control pedestrian inflow, and reasonably increase the number and width of exits. Xue et al. [27] proposed an improved FFCA model, which provided theoretical support for understanding the evolution rule of the counter flow. Li et al. [28] established an exit selection model based on cellular automata model to describe the movement rule of students in the university canteen, and proposed a facility layout that was conducive to improving the evacuation efficiency. Although the cellular automata model is easy to understand and implement, the direction of pedestrian motion is limited by discrete grids and the simulation accuracy is difficult to guarantee [29]. Lattice gas model, as a special cellular automata model, focuses on using simple local interaction rules to reflect the overall behavior of complex systems after a certain period of evolution. Tajima et al. [30] used the lattice gas model to study the downward movement of people in an open boundary T-shaped channel. Jiang et al. [31] used the improved lattice gas model to study the relationship between speed and density in pedestrian flow. The rough grid division method in the lattice gas model is not conducive to the simulation of the complex pedestrian movement rules, especially not suitable for simulating the movement of high-density crowd. The social force model uses Newton's second law to model pedestrian motion. The acceleration of pedestrian motion is jointly determined by its own desires, the influence of other pedestrians and obstacles. It can reproduce the phenomenon of self-organization such as lane formation, zipper effect [32]. Yang et al. [33] used the improved social force model to simulate the boarding and alighting behavior of passengers in the metro scene. (2) Analysis of the impact of pedestrian behavior and sites on evacuation efficiency. Some self-organization behaviors of pedestrians such as herding behavior, arching and different scenarios may affect the evacuation efficiency in case of emergency. The evacuation behavior of passengers in metro stations built in underground space is often different from that in other scenarios. (3) Introduction and

station. Sun et al. [34] proposed a crowd evacuation method based on density navigation algorithm, which effectively improved the evacuation efficiency. Zhao et al. [35] proposed a dynamic path planning algorithm based on an improved artificial bee colony, which was combined with the social force model to provide path decision-making for pedestrians. In general, the spatiotemporal continuous social force model is more realistic for the simulation of pedestrian movement compared with the existing typical motion models. This paper, therefore, selects it to simulate the movement of passengers in the metro station.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

The behavioral characteristics at the strategic level, tactical level and executive level are involved [11] in the process of passenger evacuation in the metro station. Generally, the strategic level information, such as the purpose of evacuation, is known. The tactical level information such as the specific evacuation route and the executive level information such as the specific passenger movement behavior can be simulated through the appropriate modeling. Some special pedestrian motion simulation software has emerged in succession with the rapid development of pedestrian dynamics theory and computer technology. They can be used to simulate passenger evacuation in metro stations, avoiding the dangers of human experiments and the emergence of some ethical issues that may be involved. The relevant literature review of this paper is mainly divided into the following four aspects. (1) Introduction of the existing typical pedestrian motion model. To a certain extent, the accuracy of the simulation results of evacuation is determined by the pedestrian motion model. Choosing an appropriate pedestrian motion model is convenient for the selection of simulation software and the simulation of the real evacuation

comparison existing evacuation strategies. Evacuation strategy directly determines the evacuation efficiency. Clarifying the shortcomings of existing evacuation strategies can help to improve the multi objective route optimization model constructed in this paper.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In this paper we propose an evacuation route optimization model considering passenger heterogeneity is provided. Taking minimizing the maximum evacuation time of heterogeneous passengers in different segmentation areas as the goal, it can achieve local optimization on the basis of global optimization and effectively improve the evacuation efficiency. A new method for predicting the traffic efficiency of key nodes such as gates and stairs is provided. The BP neural network model is improved by the atomic orbital algorithm to increase the accuracy of the prediction results of node travel time.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig 1: System Architecture

5. ALGORITHM

Inputs:

- Objective function: The function to be optimized.
- Search space: The range of possible values for the solution.
- Population size: The number of candidate solutions.
- Algorithm parameters: Control parameters that affect the algorithm's behavior (e.g., probability of random movement).

Step 1: Environment Modeling:

- Create a digital representation of the environment (building, city, etc.). This includes:
 - Layout of rooms, corridors, and exits.
 - Obstacle locations.

- Capacity of pathways and exits.

- Divide the space into a grid or network for computational analysis.

Step 2: Passenger Modeling:

- Define the characteristics of individual passengers (agents):
 - Location.
 - Movement speed.
 - Mobility limitations (e.g., elderly, disabled).
 - Behavioral factors (e.g., panic levels).
- Assign these characteristics to each agent in the simulation.

Step 3: Potential Field Generation (or Network Weighting):

- Potential Field Approach:
 - Assign "potential" values to each point in the environment.
 - Exits have the lowest potential.
 - Obstacles and high-density areas have higher potentials.
 - This creates a "field" that guides agents towards exits.
- Network Weighting Approach:
 - When using a network model, assign weights to the pathways of the network.
 - Weights represent the cost of traversing that pathway. Factors that effect the weight include: distance, capacity, and estimated crowd density.

Step 4: Route Calculation and Agent Movement:

- Use an optimization algorithm (e.g., Dijkstra's algorithm, A* search) or potential field gradient descent to determine the optimal route for each agent.
- Agents move along their calculated routes.
- Simulate interactions between agents (e.g., collision avoidance, congestion).
- Agent movement is updated in discrete time steps.

Step 5: Dynamic Updates:

- Continuously update the potential field or network weights based on:
 - Changing crowd density.
 - Obstacle changes.

- o Blocked exits.
 - Recalculate routes as needed.
- Step 6: Heterogeneity Considerations:**
- Adjust movement speed and route preferences based on individual passenger characteristics.
 - Prioritize routes for vulnerable passengers.
 - Simulate the impact of different passenger behaviors.

Step 7: Evaluation:

- Measure evacuation time, crowd density, and other relevant metrics.
- Analyze the effectiveness of the evacuation plan.
- Iterate and refine the algorithm as needed

Outputs:

- **Optimized Routes:**
 - o The output should provide routes that minimize evacuation time and maximize safety.
- **Dynamic Updates:**
 - o In real-time applications, the output should be able to adapt to changing conditions, such as blocked exits or changes in crowd density.
- **Accessibility:**
 - o The output should be accessible and understandable to all individuals, including those with
 - o disabilities.

6. RESULTS

6.1 Output Screens

Fig 6.1 User Login Page
In above screen shows the Login page of the User.

Fig 6.2 Upload the Datasets
In above screen shows the Upload the Datasets

Fig 6.3 View All Data Sets
In above screen shows upload the all the datasets.

Fig 6.4 View all the datasets
In above screen shows all the available datasets

Fig 6.5 Evacuation Routes or Gates AOS Algorithm using Hash code
In above screen shows the Evacuation Routes or Gates AOS Algorithm using Hash code

Fig 6.6 Find Evacuation Route

In above screen shows the to find the evacuation route

Fig 6.7 Group of evacuation Routes results in Bar Chart Graph

In above screen shows the evacuation Routes results in Bar Chart Graph.

7. CONCLUSION

Passengers in the metro station usually require to be evacuated in the case of potential safety hazards or large-scale power failure. A multi-objective optimization model of evacuation route for passengers in metro stations is established, which aims to minimize the maximum evacuation time of heterogeneous passengers in different segmentation areas. The capacity of gate, stair/escalator and exit is also considered based on the proposed AOSBP prediction model when calculating the total evacuation time. The passenger heterogeneity is classified into 9 types, the numbers of passengers with different attributes, exit width and node type are taken as the input values of the AOSBP model, and the node travel time is taken as the output value. The passenger evacuation system in the metro station is established based on Mass Motion, which can run the proposed multi-objective route optimization model. Taking the May Fourth Square metro station in Qingdao, China as a case study, the effectiveness of the route optimization model proposed in this paper is verified. The simulation results reflect that: (1) the performance of the node travel

time prediction model is good, and MSE is as low as 0.2555. With the increase of the number of iterations, the MSE has been declining. (2) The route optimization strategy can improve the overall evacuation efficiency by 21.5%, and passengers' choice of exit is more reasonable. (3) Sensitivity analysis shows that the number of passengers with attribute E has the greatest impact on the evacuation time, and they should be the focus of attention in the evacuation process. The proposed evacuation strategy can significantly improve the level of service of the metro station. However, this study has some limitations. The attributes of passengers are not diverse enough in this paper, and the impact of some special groups on evacuation behavior has not been considered. Besides, the impact of special events such as fire, flood and terrorist attacks on evacuation is not considered in this paper. This will undoubtedly bring great challenges to the evacuation management of metro stations. Our future work will focus on the above issues to carry out more in-depth explorations.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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